

SERVICE QUALITY MANAGEMENT AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION FOR HOTEL SERVICE IN ABUJA NIGERIA.

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Abstract: *The aim of this study is to identify how service quality tools can be managed to realize customer satisfaction for hotel services. This research was carried out with six 5-star hotels located within Abuja. This research is designed in a descriptive approach. A population of 780 and sample size of 264 guests were administered with a structured questionnaire distributed through a convenience sampling technique. Data obtained was analyzed through descriptive statistics, while the multiple regression analysis model was used to test the hypothesis. The results from Data analysis and hypothesis testing show that Reliability, Assurance, Empathy and Responsiveness have strong significant relationship while tangibles have weak relationship with Customer Satisfaction for Hotel Services. Based on the findings the study recommends that Hotels should: provide customers with services that represent the value they have paid for; be able to deliver services promptly when, where and how needed by customers; show courtesy and convey trust and confidence to customers; provide care and individualized attention to customers, provide physical evidence that would convey ability to deliver value to customers.*

Introduction

Services are intangible product offers that satisfy needs. Because of their intangible nature and variability feature, it is difficult to substantiate the quality of services (Madu & Hindu, 2020). Because of the difficulty associated with predicting the quality of services and customer satisfaction for services, there is need for special consideration for services quality management. Service offering is a production of an essentially intangible benefit, either in its own right, or as a significant element of a tangible product, which

through some form of exchange satisfies an identified need (Palmer, 2005). This special consideration is mainly determined by the special features of services. Madu, et.al., 2016 reveal that services possess unique characteristics, and that these characteristics are summarized as Intangibility, Perishability, Inseparability, and Variability.

The Intangible nature of services means that services cannot be perceived through any of the sensory organs, though tangible factors can be used to provide the services. The Perishability

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nature of services means that services cannot be stored or warehoused. Services are consumed while produced through the interaction between the producer and the consumer. The Inseparability nature of service means that production and consumption are simultaneous. Just like the perishability feature, Services are consumed while produced through the interaction between the producer and the consumer. The Variability nature of services means that the quality of services cannot be perceived as the same among the customers. There must always be some variations any time a service is offered to different customers, and most times even to the same customers.

Hotel is a business activity that provides foods, drinks and decent accommodations through their bars, restaurants and guest rooms (Kotler, Bowen and Makens, 2006). Webster, 2000 also refers hotel to represent a tool used to provide hospitality and leisure to customers. The implication of these definitions is that every good or decent hotel must be able to offer and provide hospitality and leisure to customers. Kotler, et. al., 2006 further state that hotel is a segment of hospitality which consists of any location designed to accommodate a guest for one or more night's rest. This means that hotel is the main tool for hospitality and tourism industry. The implication of this is that all other activities need the provision of decent hotel to be consummated

Despite the enormous opportunities in the hotel business in Abuja, many hostels in Abuja still have difficulty in making profits (Adeola &

Ezenwafor, 2016). This problem has been traced to be as a result of low customer patronage caused by lack of customer satisfaction for service quality by hotel operators and their employees (Kotler, Bowen and Makens, 2006). On his part, Mistry, 2023 gave the major challenges associated with operating profitable hotel businesses in cities of modern societies like Abuja to include: employee's skills and behavior, change in marketing trends, dynamic operational issues, technological changes, incessant activities of competitors, among other things. But what is paramount is loyalty to the hotel by customers. If the hotels are able to attract and retain customer's loyalty through service quality, the impact of all the problems and challenges enumerated above will be insignificant as they would have been prevented. Since these challenges are part of external environmental factors beyond the control of the hotel managers, the managers have no option other than to utilize its strength which is the provision and management of quality service. Therefore, the aim of this study is to identify how best to utilize service quality tools such as reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness for customers satisfaction in the hotel business.

Research Objectives

The aim of this study is to identify the extent of relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction for hotel services. Specific objectives include to:

1. Ascertain the nature of impact that service reliability has on customer satisfaction for hotel services.
2. Determine how employee's assurance affect customer satisfaction for hotel services.
3. Identify the relationship between tangible evidence and customer satisfaction for hotels services.
4. Discover the degree of relationship between employees empathy and customer satisfaction for hotel services.
5. Know if employees service reliability affect customer satisfaction for hotel services.

Research Question

What is the nature of relationship between services quality and customer satisfaction for hotel services?

Research Hypothesis

Service Quality has no significant relationship with Customer Satisfaction for hotel services.

Methodology

To realize the objectives of this study and also provide solutions to the research questions, this research was carried out with six 5-star hotels located within the central business district area of the Federal Capital Territory Abuja. This research is designed in a descriptive approach with observation and questionnaire as sources of primary data. A population of 780 guests in these 5-star hotels were observed within two weeks based on sample size of 264 determined through Taro Yamene method of sample size determination. A structured questionnaire was distributed to the guests according to the percentage of population contributed by the

selected 5-star hotels. The questionnaire was distributed through a convenience sampling technique. Data obtained was analyzed through descriptive and inferential statistics, while the multiple regression analysis model was used to test the hypothesis postulated.

Literature Review

Service Quality

Service quality is the ability of services rendered to conform to the requirements by customers. This means that the quality of a service depends on the experience of the customer (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2000). In the Hospitality and Hotel industry, it is somehow difficult to realize quality which is determined by customer satisfaction. This is because the Hospitality and Hotel industry involves a high degree of contact and coordination between employees and guest. Total quality can never be achieved because employees must make mistakes, and system will once in a while fail (Palmer, 2005). This therefore gave rise to the need for the development of services quality measurement. After an extensive research, Berry & Parasuraman, 1991 came up with five general dimensions that influence customer assessment of service quality. These dimensions are: Reliability, Tangibles, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy.

Reliability

This means the ability to perform the promised hotel services dependably and accurately (Giovanni, 2012). Customers to a hotel come with anticipated performance in the form of customers' expectation and satisfaction.

Professionally, a customer to a hotel is termed a guest. A guest is a special feature of visitor who has paid for absolute comfort in the form of leisure and relaxation. What determines the reliability of a good or customer-oriented hotel is its ability to provide the customers (guests) with their request how, when and where they need it. This is what makes a hotel service reliable. Berry & Parasuraman, 1991 states that reliability is the essence of service quality. If a guest in a hotel is unable to get the services, he/she has paid for when, where, and how he needs the services, he/she will be dissatisfied and will likely switch patronage to competitors.

Tangibles

This represents the visibility and appearance of physical facilities, equipments, personnel, and communication materials (Futrell, 2006). They include the ability of the hotels to showcase or ensure the appearance, availability and functionality of physical facilities, and relevant visible facilities that portrays the ability of the hotel to render quality services. Since the quality of hotel services is not stored anywhere to enable the guests access the ability of the hotel to provide quality services, the guest can only predetermine quality service by the hotel through the visibility of tangible objects positioned as tools for hotel quality service (Dunne and Lusch, 1999). For example, an intending guest arriving a hotel will need to be assured that the hotel has adequate security. Otherwise, he may be afraid and either ask or go to another hotel where adequate security is guaranteed. Therefore, positioning armed

security personnel at the entrance gate can do this magic. Other examples of tangible evidence include well-light environment with steady electricity, neatly dressed employees, attractive colors and flowers.

Responsiveness

This means the willingness to help customers and to provide prompt services when, where and how they are needed (Berry & Parasuraman, 1991). It practically implies the willingness to deliver prompt hotel service to the guest. Though this depends on the accuracy of the service tools available in that particular hotel. These services tools in the hotels also depend on technological advancements and the ability of the hotel to adhere to and cope with them as they emerge. For instance, a faulty intercom or telecommunication facility in the rooms and unsteady electricity may disrupt quality and prompt response or services to the guest by the hotel employees. Some measures by the hotel that constitute responsiveness to guest include: Promptness in responding to guest complaints and or inquiries; reducing the steps and length for delivering and receiving services to guest; flexibility and ability to customize services according to guest needs; constantly requesting and obtaining feedback from guest on their satisfaction of the quality of services they receive from the hotel; and continuous improvements on the quality of services to the guests based on guests request (Brassington and Pettitt, 2006).

Assurance

This represents the knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to convey trust and

confidence to customers ((Giovanni, 2012). Practically, assurance as a tool for service quality in the hotel industry is the ability of employees in the hotel to show courtesy and to convey trust and confidence to the guest. The room service personnel, the waiter, the desk officers and even the cleaners represent the management and product of the hotel (Cravens and Piercy, 2003). They must be courteous and must be able to convey trust to the guest. The key to achieving this is sincerity and friendliness at all times.

Empathy

This means the provision of caring, and individualized attention given to customers by employees of the hotel (Adeola and Ezenwafor, 2020). In practical terms, it is the ability of hotels employees to freely and willingly provide caring and individualized attention to guests. This can be realized through listening to guests when they call or make complaints and providing or offering solutions to their request when they have such.

Customer satisfaction

To have an adequate understanding of customer satisfaction, it is important to understand the meaning of customer value. Customer value can be described as the difference between the actual or measurable benefits that the customer gets from owning or using a product and the actual costs of obtaining the product (Futrell, 2003). The said cost can be in monetary or nonmonetary. In high caliber hotels in Abuja Central District Area, time is the most fascinating nonmonetary cost to customers. It is improper to expect an executive guest to queue in a line to

book for a room, or expect him/her to wait for more than the time promised to deliver a meal or laundry service. These are factors that constitute value to customers in high Caliber hotels.

Customer satisfaction is the ability of the company to satisfy customer needs. Kotler et.al., 2006 state that the customer satisfaction depends on product-perceived performance in delivering value compared to customers expectation. If the product's performance falls short of customer's expectation, the buyer is dissatisfied; if the performance matches the expectation, the buyer is satisfied; but if performance exceeds expectation, the buyer is delighted. Jobber, 2004 therefore recommends that smart companies should aim to delight customers by promising what they can deliver and striving to deliver more than they have promised.

The marketing concept established the fact that the customer is the king (Brassington and Pettitt: 2006). This means that, until the customer is satisfied, all efforts for service delivery is a waste. Copley, 2017 identifies six (6) reasons why customer satisfaction is important, these reasons include: it is an indicator of customers' repeat purchase and patronage or loyalty; it is used as a key differentiator among competing organizations; it is used to avoid customers' agitation over an organizations' service; it increases customers lifeline value (CLV) which is also an increase in revenue accruable to the service organization; customer satisfaction reduces negative word of mouth by the customer against the organization; and it enables the

organization retain existing customers which is cheaper than acquiring new ones. When a customer is satisfied with the services received from a hotel, patronage to that hotel will be guaranteed.

Theoretical Framework

RATER Model

This model (theory) was propounded by Berry and Parasuraman, 1991. In the theory, Berry & Parasuraman, 1991 state that common sense underscores the importance of reliability in delivering quality service. This means that reliability is the foremost criterion that customers consider in evaluating a firm's quality or service. Nevertheless, reliability is not the only factor that determines the quality of service. After an extensive research effort, Berry & Parasuraman, 1991 suggested five general dimensions that influence customer's assessment of service quality. These dimensions include reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness (that is the acronym 'RATER' where R is Responsibility; A is Assurance; T is Tangible; E is Empathy; and R is Responsiveness).

These dimensions have been briefly explained earlier in this chapter. Berry & Parasuramen, 1991 further state that reliability has repeatedly emerged as the most critical dimension in every study concerning services quality measurement in which they have measured the relative importance of the five dimensions. The model was later defined by some followers of Berry & Parasuraman, 1991. The model is also known as service quality model.

The underpinning theory for this study is the RATER Model. This model (theory) was propounded by Berry and Parasuraman, 1991. The reason behind this decision is because the theory explains the appropriate service quality tools to be taken by services firms in Hospitality and Hotel Industry to ensure customer satisfaction, which will guarantee customer patronage. These service quality tools include: Reliability (R), Assurance (A), Tangibles (T), Empathy (E), and Responsiveness (R).

Empirical Review

A study on "The Hospitality in Nigeria: Issues, Challenges and Opportunities" was executed by Adeola and Ezenwafor, 2020. The paper aims to advance cooperation and collaboration as solutions to problems in the Nigeria hospitality industry. A small independent restaurant in Lagos was used as the case of study. The phenomenological research strategy guided the approach to the study. Primary data was gathered through one to one interview to ascertain how individuals within a defined industry experienced the verifications of the phenomenon. The major findings include that the operating environment of the hospitality sector in Nigeria has an effect on the supply of skills and the financial performance of the case restaurant and similar hospitality business. The study therefore recommends that to improve overall performance of the industry, private public partnership between government agencies, hospitality colleges and hospitality business, strategic partnership between expert hospitality institutions and businesses schools,

cooperation among hospitality business owners and improvements in managerial practices could be strategic moves for an industry operating under institutional hindrances peculiar to Nigeria. This study is relevant to our study as it provides an all-encompassing approach to profitable operations of all parts of the hospitality industry

In a study titled “A Review of the Hotel Industry in Nigeria: Size, structure and issues”, Nwosu, 2022, provided an overview of the dynamics that define, govern and shape the tourism and hospitality sector in Nigeria in particular the hotel industry with respect to its size, structure and salient issues that impact on it. Primary survey data from STR Global was used. Also, content analysis of secondary data from government education and industry sources were used to identify the issues within the industry. Major findings from the study show: positive indicators for employment and further expansion within the hotel sector in Nigeria; the lack of supporting institutions, legal framework and industry representation makes the management of human resources an area of concern. The study recommends the need for a research agenda for the hospitality and tourism industry in Nigeria. This will further create the framework to understand and improve best practices particularly with institutional framework, employments and human capital development. This study is relevant to our study as it emphasis the need for human capital development which is currently lacking in the

Nigeria hotel business and which is part of the objectives of the study.

The study titled “The Meaning of Hospitality: Do employees understand”, was executed by Golubouskays, Robinson, and Solnet, 2021. This paper explores how hospitality frontline employees understand, interpret and practice “hospitality” in a hotel industry context. The study was framed with interpretive and phenomenological approaches with dual stage semi-structured interview study design. Primary data was obtained from hotel employees in Australia. The major findings include a support for the proposition that the hospitality workforce tends to favor service management and service process as the guiding paradigm; the essence of what it means to be hospitable and the host guest model appear to be largely assented. Based on the findings, the authors advocate an inter-paradigmatic view of hospitality managements. The study is relevant to our study as it also reveals the importance of employees in the hotels towards profitable service delivery through customer satisfaction and retention.

Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction: A case study of hotel industry in Vietnam, was executed by Minh, Ha, Anih, and Matsiu, 2022. The purpose of this study is to empirically examine the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in Vietnam hotels. Survey questionnaire was constructed with 23 service quality items covering five (5) quality dimensions based on SERVQUAL Model. Data were collected from 432 guests of 33 3-star hotels in Vietnam in 2013. The result of data analysis

shows that reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy significantly impact on customer satisfaction. The study therefore recommends that hotel managers should focus on Empathy, reliability, responsiveness and assurance to achieve high degree of customer satisfaction which leads to customer loyalty and business profit. This study is relevant to our study because it emphasized on service quality and its impact on hotel customers satisfaction which is one of the proxies of this study.

The study titled “Hotel Service Quality: The Impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in hospitality industry” was executed by Ali, et.al., 2021. The purpose of this study was to reveal the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in hotels. Questionnaire was administered to guest in hotel in Erbil city in Kurdistan region. Data gathered was analyzed through quantitative method. The result of the analyses reveals that apart from reliability, other service quality factors (responsiveness, assurance, tangibles and empathy) have significant relationships with customer’s satisfaction for hotels. The study therefore recommends that managers should constantly adjust responsiveness, assurance, tangibles and empathy to suit customer’s satisfaction. This study is relevant to our study because it explains the impact of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction for hotel services.

Service Delivery and Customer Satisfaction in Hospitality Industry: A Study of Devine Fountain Hotels Limited, Lagos Nigeria was executed by Kukogi and Iwagwu, 2021 This study

investigated the relationship between service delivery and customer satisfaction at the Devine Fountain Hotels Limited in Lagos Nigeria. Primary data were gathered through Questionnaire and interview methods. 400 guests were administered with a questionnaire and interview through convenient sampling method. Data collected were analyzed using frequency counts, percentage and chart. The major findings include that the hotel offers a variety of customer-centric services which are satisfactory to their customers, and this has helped the hotel retain loyal customers over significant period of time; the two variables, service delivery and customer satisfaction are significantly related. Hence, they predict the growth, improve quality of services offered, increases patronage and revenue. The study recommends that: in order to keep the good performance of the hotel, the hotel should always get feedback from her customers; management of the hotel should maintain quality service delivery which has contributed to the growth of the hotel. This study is relevant to our study because it succinctly describes the relevance of service delivery towards achieving customer satisfaction and patronage in hotels which is the aim of this study.

‘Customer Service Experience in Hotel Operations: An Empirical Analysis’ was carried out by Khan, Ruchi and Rahman, 2021. This study aimed at bringing an understanding of customers experience quality in hotel operations. The study adopted customer experience scale and examined its effect on customer satisfaction,

brand loyalty and word of mouth in the hotel industry. The primary data was obtained from 326 hotel guests from Waridivar and Dehradun Districts in India through a questionnaire. The questions were anchored on customer experience quality scale, loyalty, customer satisfaction and word of mouth. Data obtained were tested through regression model. The major findings confirm that there is positive and significant influence of all four-customer experience quality (EXQ) dimensions on consumer behavioral outcomes; that customer evaluation is not only based on service

encounters, but also includes every touch point with an organization; and that customer experience has effect on customers patronage as a behavioral outcome. The study therefore advocates collective efforts by all employees of a service organization to ensure a positive experience by the customer. The study is related to our study because customers experience is one of the determinants of customer patronage for a hotel and is one of the major pillars of our study.

Data Analysis and Result

Residence of Respondents

Table 4.3: COUNTRY OF RESIDENCE

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Nigeria	208	80.0	80.0	80.0
	Outside Nigeria	52	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	260	100.0	100.0	

Source:SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires" Data 2023).

Table 4.3 shows the analysis of country of residence of the respondents. It reveals that 208 which represent 80% frequency reside in Nigeria while 52 of our respondents representing 20% reside outside Nigeria.

Patronage of Hotel in Abuja

Table 4.6 FREQUENT PATRONAGE OF HOTELS IN ABUJA

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Often	150	57.7	57.7	57.7
	Often	52	20.0	20.0	77.7
	Rarely	6	2.3	2.3	80.0
	First Time	52	20.0	20.0	100.0

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Total 260 100.0 100.0

Source:SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires” Data 2023).

Table 4.6 analyzed frequent patronage of hotels in Abuja by respondents. The tables shows that 150 respondents representing 57.7% patronize hotels in Abuja very often; 52 frequencies representing 20% answered often; 6 frequencies representing 2.3% answered rarely while 52 frequencies representing 20% of the total respondents indicated that they patronized hotels in Abuja for the first time.

Univariate Analysis

This section is primarily concerned with the analysis of univariate variables relating to the respondents’ views on the questions contained in the research instruments of the study. The primary analysis entailed the assessment of the distribution and applications of statistical analysis on each variable as a means of examining the tendencies of these variables. The research instrument generated data that showed the degree of agreement of the major

variable, as well as the dimensions and measures.

The data obtained from the field was measured using a 5-point Likert scale based on Very High Extent (VHE) /Strongly Agree (SA) (5); High Extent (HE) /Agree (A) (4); Moderate Extent (ME) /Undecided (UD) (3); Low Extent (LE) /Disagree (DIS) (2) and Very Low Extent(VLE) /Strongly Disagree (SD) (1). As such interpretations for each variable is premised on the extent to which it’s mean distributions reflect either significant evidence (where $x > 3.0$) or the extent to which it reflects insignificant evidence (where $x < 3.0$). Based on this, the research question was analysed.

Research Question

To what extent does service quality impact on customer satisfaction of Hotel service in Abuja?

Table 4.19: Computation of Mean Responses on the impact of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction of Hotel Service in Abuja

Descriptive Statistics

Indicators	N	Min	Max	Sum	Std.		
					Mean	Deviation	Variance
SERVICE QUALITY	260	1.00	5.00	1053.67	4.0526	.73142	.535

You are satisfied with the service quality of this hotel,260 1 5 1044 4.02 .669 .448 and based on this you are willing to maintain patronage for the hotel.

You are satisfied with the level of reliability for the260 services in this hotel, and based on this you are willing to maintain your patronage for the hotel.	1	5	1098	4.22	.845	.715
You are satisfied with the level of assurance for good260 services in this hotel, and based on this you are willing to maintain your patronage for the hotel.	1	5	1042	4.01	.697	.486
You are satisfied with the tangible facilities seen260 around this hotel, and based on this you are willing to maintain your patronage for the hotel.	1	5	968	3.72	.834	.695
You are satisfied with the level of empathy shown by260 employees of this hotel, and based on this you are willing to maintain your patronage for the hotel.	1	5	1106	4.25	.769	.592
You are satisfied with the level of responsiveness of260 the services in this hotel, and based on this you are willing to maintain your patronage for the hotel.	1	5	1064	4.09	.917	.841

Valid N (listwise) 260

Source: SPSS output (Base on questionnaires' data 2023)

Table 4.19 illustrates the summary of the analysis from statistics on service quality impact and customer satisfaction of hotels service in Abuja with summarized values for central tendency based on the responses to the indicators. The analysis revealed that all indicators on the scale had mean scores above the criterion mean of 3.00 on a 5-point likert scale. With the grand mean of 4.05 the respondents agreed to a high extent that service quality impacts on customer satisfaction of hotel service in Abuja.

Bivariate Analyses and Test of Hypothesis

The bivariate relationship determination in this section was done using Simple Linear Regression in the assessment of the relationship between the dimensions of service quality management and customer satisfaction.

Thus, in determining the respective strength and statistical relationship of the association between these variables, the researcher was guided by the work of Cohen et al., 2007. The

coefficient of correlation (effect size) the strength of association and statistically significant decision according to Cohen, et al., 2007 is interpreted below.

Table 4.23: Cohen et al statistical correlation decision scale frame

S/N	Statistical Significance	Association
i.	0.1 – 0.29	Very Weak
ii.	0.3 – 0.49	Weak
iii.	0.5 – 0.69	Moderate
iv.	0.70 – 0.79	Strong
v.	0.80 – 1.00	Very strong

Source: Cohen et al ,2007.

Cohen et al (2007) posit that, effect size is an easy way to quantify both relationship and difference between two groups and at the same time to measure the effectiveness and statistical significance. Generally, the decision rule for the acceptance or rejection of hypothetical statements is premised on the adoption of a 0.05 significance threshold due to its 95% test on all hypotheses.

The formulae:

$$Y = a + bX + \epsilon$$

Where:

Y – Dependent variable

Table 4.23: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.987 ^a	.975	.975	.10583	.186

a. Predictors: (Constant), SERVICE QUALITY

b. Dependent Variable: CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Source: SPSS output (2023)

X – Independent (explanatory) variable

a – Intercept

b – Slope

ε – Residual (error)

Decision Rule

If the probability value (PV) in the coefficient table is less than 0.05 alpha level, we Reject the null hypotheses and accept the alternate hypotheses of significant relationship.

If the probability value (PV) is greater than 0.05 alpha level, we accept the null hypothesis of no significant relationship. The data is thus analysed below.

This table provides the R and R² values. The R value represents the simple correlation and is 0.987^a (the "R" Column), which indicates a high degree of correlation. The R² value (the "R Square" column) indicates that 97.5% of the total variation in the dependent variable, Customer Satisfaction' can be explained by the independent variable, Service Quality'which is very large.The Durbin-Watson "d" = .186, is between the two critical values of 1.5 < d < 2.5 and therefore we can assume that there is no first order linear auto-correlation in the data. Hence the model is of absolute good fit.

Table 4.24: ANOVA

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	111.433	1	111.433	9948.652	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.890	258	.011		
	Total	114.323	259			

a. Dependent Variable: CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

b. Predictors: (Constant), SERVICE QUALITY

Source: SPSS output (2023)

The probability value of 0.000 indicates that the regression relationship was significant in determining how Service Quality impact on Customer Satisfaction of hotels service in Abuja. The F calculated at 5 percent level of significance was 9948.652 which is greater than the F critical (value = 2.4472), this shows that the overall model was significant. Also the p < 0.000, is less than 0.05, and indicates that, overall, the regression model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable (i.e., it is a good fit for the data).

Table 4.25: Coefficients^a

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.482	.037		13.013	.000
	SERVICE QUALITY	.897	.009	.987	99.743	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Source: SPSS output (2023)

The regression results in table 4.25above shows a model constant (a) value of 0.482 and Service Quality value of 0.897, indicating that, for every one percent increase inService Quality, the

dependent variable 'Customer Satisfaction' will rise by 89%. T-value produced 13.013, is significant at P value (.000), which is less than the chosen alpha of α (0.05). Thus, hypothesis

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one which states that service quality has no impact on the customer satisfaction for hotels services in Abuja is rejected. This implies that a very strong significant relationship exists between service quality and customer satisfaction of hotel service in Abuja.

Summary of Findings

The results from Data analysis and hypothesis testing shows that of all the Service Quality variables, Reliability, Assurance, Empathy and Responsiveness have strong significant relationship with Customer Satisfaction for Hotel Services.

Conclusion

From our review and discussion so far, we can deduce that service quality measures including reliability, responsiveness, tangibles, assurance, and empathy determines the quality of service provided by hotels that satisfy guests and guarantees guests continuous patronage for the hotels in Abuja. But Reliability, Assurance, Empathy and Responsiveness have strong significant relationship with Customer Satisfaction for Hotel Services. Therefore, for hotels in Abuja to make profit and remain in business through consistent customer patronage, the hotel management should utilize the effective and efficient management of service quality tools including reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

Recommendations

Based on the Findings and Conclusion, the study recommends that Hotel Employees should:

- i. Provide customers with services that are reliable, dependable and represent the value they have paid for.
- ii. Be able to deliver services promptly when, where and how needed by customers.
- iii. Show courtesy and convey trust and confidence to customers.
- iv. Provide care and individualized attention to customers.
- v. Provide physical evidence such as armed security, constant light and neatly dressed personnel that would convey trust and ability to deliver value to customers.

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